

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE VIBRATIONS OF COMPOSITE RING SPECIMENS UNDER INTERNAL IMPULSE LOADING

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ABSTRACTS

The possibility of determining the elastic properties and buffer response to free damped vibrations of ring specimens loaded from inside by explosion of a linear charge of high explosive is shown in the present paper for unidirectional plastic composite materials, reinforced by glass, organic, combining glass and organic fibers and carbon fibers.

INTRODUCTION

In modern mechanical engineering such properties of structure materials as dynamic strength and ability to scatter elastic energy under vibrations and impacts acquire a significance among the traditional properties like rigidity, strength, hardness. Unlike those of metals and their alloys, the dissipative properties of composites are high and their logarithmic decrement is by an order of magnitude higher than that of metals, while their elasticity modulus is compatible with that of metals (and often is higher). Therefore, determination of these properties is of high interest for application purposes.

One of the most wide-spread experimental techniques for determining the viscoelastic and vibration absorbing properties of the composite materials is the method of free damped vibrations [1], which, as a rule, applies bending (more rarely, twisting) vibrations of freely suspended or supported as a cantilever beams of rectangular or circular cross section. In the case the measurement results for freely suspended beams can be essentially affected by the conditions of fastening and inducing the vibrations, and for cantilever beams, by the nonuniformity of stress-strained state. For a unidirectional composite the logarithmic attenuation decrement depends substantially on concentration of reinforcing fibers, on the type of a binder and on relative content of fibers of different types in combined composites [2]. Certain technological problems arise when producing flat specimens of a unidirectional fibrous composite designed for determining the damping characteristics from free damped vibrations of cantilever-supported or freely suspended specimen.

The series of works [3,4,5] is present in which the ring specimens (RS) were used for research of dynamic properties of metals and composites at high strain-rate loading. By the use of

RS the uniform strain-stressed state of uniaxial tension-compression is produced, which is impossible in long flat specimens, since initial load cannot be applied simultaneously over the whole surface of the specimen. When RS are made from fiber composites produced by winding at the angle close to 0° , the composite is unidirectional and with high content of reinforcing fibers (up to 70 %) and uniform for the case of combined reinforcing base (several types of reinforcing fibers in one composite) due to simultaneous laying of different types of fibers in one technological thread.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experiments on internal impulsive loading were performed at RS which were cut out from circular cylindrical shells, produced by ring winding at the angle close to 0° of four types of fibers: glass fibers (E-glass), organic (aramid) fibers, combining glass (33 %) and organic (67 %) fibers and carbon (low-strength, low-modulus, low-density porous) fibers, impregnated by ЭДТ-10 epoxy compound. The results of static tests of circular ring specimens of examined materials by means of NOL-methods (using rigid half-discs) has shown that the elasticity modulus and ultimate strength in circumferential direction are: $E_{gl} = 65.0 \pm 5$ GPa and $\sigma_{gl} = 1.54$ GPa for glass fiber composite, $E_{ar} = 116.0 \pm 5$ GPa, $\sigma_{ar} = 2.01$ GPa for organic (aramid) fiber composite, $E_{cm} = 98.5 \pm 5$ GPa and $\sigma_{cm} = 1.72$ GPa for combined composite and $E_{cb} = 95.0 \pm 5$ GPa and $\sigma_{cb} = 1.10$ GPa for carbon fiber composite respectively. The density of these materials is: glass-fiber composite - 2.03 g/cm³, organic-fiber composite - 1.32 g/cm³, combined composite - 1.55 g/cm³ and 1.35 g/cm³ for carbon-fiber composite.

Fig. 1 presents the scheme of loading of RS. A ring specimen (5) with internal diameter 100 mm, wall thickness 2 mm and height 20 mm was placed between upper (7) and bottom (3) flanges which were fastened at four studs (2), disposed coaxially at the base (11). Free vibrations of the ring in the course of vibrations was provided by restraining bushes (4) whose height was by 0.1 - 0.2 mm greater than that of RS. RS was loaded by the detonation products of a linear explosive charge (9) placed along the length of the specimen. As a charge used a piece of a cover-less detonating fusee of plastified hexogen of diameter 2 mm (or 1.4 mm) and length 200 mm. This part of the fusee was inserted in a rigid paper tube (8) which was put on a centering sleeve (10) attached to the base (11). The fusee was blasted from the end of the tube by means of a low-voltage small-size electric detonator (1) (diameter 6 mm, height 9 mm) which produces small field of fragments by an intermediate charge of bulk pre-pressed hexogen 0.4 - 0.5 g of weight. The loading was of purely pulsed character, since the duration of pressure pulse impacting on the ring wall does not exceed 2 - 3 sec with the period of free vibrations of RS 35 - 50 sec and higher.

Nonuniformity of the loading due to finiteness of velocity of detonation propagation along the charge length also was not great: with detonation velocity of the fusee 7.5 km/sec and height of the ring 20 mm the time discrepancy of the loading on the RS wall is less than 3 sec and does not introduce any noticeable error in the process of vibration of the ring. In order to diminish the nonuniformity of the loading one can reduce the ring height to 8 - 12 mm: the time discrepancy of loading in this case will decrease to 1 - 1.5 sec. The hoop strain of RS was registered by a circular resistance strain gauge (6) made by winding ten full turns of insulated resistance wire around the cylindrical wall of RS, analogous to that applied in [6]. The wire used was ПЭХХ-0.1 nichrome wire 0.1 mm in diameter and with a resistance of 135 Ω /m. Gauge was bonded to the outer surface of composite RS by epoxy resin ЭД-20 of cold curing with addition of 20 weight % of plasticizer (dibutylfthalate). The

use of this gauges for registration of averaged hoop strain of RS during the experiments allows, which, on one hand, to exclude the undesirable bending of RS wall, and, on the other hand, to determine the hoop strain of the ring wall for the whole length at once.

Figure 1. Equipment for ring specimen loading

Fig. 2 presents typical oscillograms of free damped vibrations of RS made of glass-plastic (a), organoplastic (b), combine glass-organic (c) and carbon reinforced (d) composites.

Figure 2. Typical oscilloscope traces from the free damped vibrations of ring specimens

In the case of radial vibrations the axis of RS forms a circle with periodically changing radius and all transversal sections of the ring move radially without rotation. In [7] the frequency of the free vibrations of thin-wall ring is determined from the formula

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi R} \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}} \quad (1)$$

where R is the internal radius of the ring, E is the elasticity modulus of the ring material, and ρ is the density of the ring material.

To estimate the accuracy of determining the elastic characteristics of RS material the composite RS was loaded by static rigid half-discs prior to impulsive loading and the elasticity modulus of the specimen was determined. "Theoretical" value of the frequency f_{theor} of free vibrations was determined from this value of elasticity modulus according to Eqn 1. The free-vibration frequency experimentally determined after impulsive loading of RS was compared to the theoretical value. The "experimental" frequency f_{exper} was determined from the number of vibration periods of RS from the beginning of the vibration process to its complete attenuation. The difference between the values f_{theor} and f_{exper} did not exceed 2 - 5 %.

Experimental results are presented in the Table 1 (averaging from three specimens each of composites type). Comparison of the values of f_{theor} and f_{exper} shows that with this loading technique RS makes free damped vibrations of purely radial mode with its lowest natural frequency. The process of vibrations is steady and the vibrations of higher modes fail to excite. The values of logarithmic attenuation decrement δ_{exper} were determined from first ten and twenty vibration periods. It should be noted that the value of the attenuation decrement strongly depends on the level of acting stresses for metals and to a higher degree for composites. To construct a functional dependence of the decrement on the stress level, one should analyze the whole process of the attenuation of vibrations. Therefore, the values δ_{exper} are of approximate character. Exact reference data for unidirectional high-strength glass-fiber-plastic and organic-fiber-plastic are lacking. The values of logarithmic attenuation decrement for low-strength glass-fiber textolites with the elasticity modulus 12 GPa and 22 GPa presented in [8] are 0.12 - 0.125 and 0.1, respectively. The value of the decrement obtained in [9], when studying the behavior of fiber-glass-plastic shells (with elasticity modulus in circumferential direction 33 GPa) under explosive loading from inside, is 0.05. Thus, the data obtained in the present work are in satisfactory agreement with the data of the other papers.

Table 1. Experimental data

composite	f_{theor} , Hz	f_{exper} , Hz	Δ , %	δ_{exper}
glass-fiber plastic	18012	17576	2.42	0.095±0.02
aramid-fiber plastic	26861	27143	1.04	0.194±0.02
combine-fiber plastic	22389	23570	5.01	0.156±0.02
carbon-fiber plastic	25954	26542	2.21	0.112±0.02

The technique proposed for studying the elastic vibrations can be a convenient tool when processing the records of the RS deformation process by the methods of spectral analysis. The absence of beats and superposition of highest frequencies in the process of vibration with the character of damped vibrations close to harmonic one, will also one to obtain a spectrum with narrow clearly marked maximum corresponding to the basic vibration frequency.

Thus, the method of loading of RS and registration of hoop strain in the process of vibrations allow for the development of considerably accurate method for determining elastic and damping properties of composite materials produced by winding.

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